

A COMPLETE ANALYSIS OF THE MODULE PROGRAM TO ASSESS THE REDUCTION OF ELECTRICITY EMISSIONS IN DISTRIBUTION TRANSFORMERS WITH EXTENSIVE USE OF THE DIFFERENTIAL TARIFF SYSTEM

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Analysis of the module program for evaluating the reduction of electricity waste
in distribution transformers using a system of differentiated tariffs

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Abstract: The following works were made in the article:

- The importance of introducing a system of differentiated tariffs today
- the possibility of reducing electricity losses in distribution transformers using a system of differentiated tariffs in the electric power system.
- analysis of a software module on information communications, which evaluates the possibilities of reducing electricity losses in distribution transformers.

Key words: differentiated tariffs, distribution transformer, communication, information communication program, module.

Introduction. The draft decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On changes in prices for fuel and energy resources” was submitted for public discussion, and price standards for the republic were determined from July 1, 2022. Two or Additional payments are made for gas and electricity consumed in excess of the established volume.

In this given article, an information communication program module that evaluates the possibilities of reducing energy waste in distribution transformers by applying a differentiated tariff system in the electric power system is analyzed. This program allows you to see the dynamics of changes in electricity load graphs by changing the current demand for electricity in various ways.

The main part. Let's look at the example of the analysis of the loss of electrical energy in the process of load change in a transformer with a power of 630 kVA. The electricity consumed by consumers is controlled by three-phase balance meters (brand EX518) connected to the network.

Information on the active and reactive energy consumed by transformer consumers with a power of 630 kVA for 5 periods is given (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Current value of consumption indicators

Below is the load graph drawn based on the readings of the balance meter installed on a three-phase power 630 kVA transformer (brand EX518) Graph 1

Figure 1. A graph drawn based on the initial indicators entered into the program

Graph 1 shows that the electricity demand of consumers is mainly in the morning and evening peak times of the day.

The program has the ability to change the indicator of consumption at all times in any way, including:

- calculate the value of wasted electricity by converting the consumed active energy values to the desired percentage (%)
- by changing the value of consumed active power and reactive power, it is possible to evaluate the result.

The following formulas are included in the program:

$$P = \frac{W}{T}; \quad (1)$$

formula The formula for calculating the value of active power

$$Q = W/T \text{ (kVAr)} \quad (2)$$

Formula 2 is the formula for calculating reactive power

$$S_{\text{period 1}} = \sqrt{P_{\text{period 1}}^2 + Q_{\text{period 1}}^2} \quad (3)$$

Formula 3 is the full power calculation formula

$$\Delta P_{\text{simple}} = \Delta P_{Q.T} \left(\frac{S_{\text{period 1}}}{S_{\text{name}}} \right)^2 + \Delta P_{C.\text{work}} \quad (4)$$

Formula 4 is a formula for finding the amount of electrical energy loss in transformers

$$\Delta \eta_{\phi} = \frac{\eta_1 - \eta_2}{\eta_1} * 100\% \quad (5)$$

Formula 5 includes a combination of basic formulas, such as formulas for finding the difference between current consumption and consumption change.

For the first case, we will change the consumption indicators by $\pm 15\%$. (Figure 2)

	Aq kVt	Rq kVar	Tq kVA	1 kunda		
1-davr	89,0	6,0	89,2	kVt soat	15	+ ▾
2-davr	503,3	34,7	504,5		15	- ▾
3-davr	128,8	6,0	128,9	67,0	0	+ ▾
4-davr	302,0	20,8	302,7		15	- ▾
5-davr	267,0	18,0	267,6		15	+ ▾

Figure 2. Distribution of the state of change of consumption indicator by 15% in periods

Figure 3. Appearance after changing values

The result shows that the waste of electricity in the distribution transformers has decreased by 7.9% compared to the current situation.

We can see that if the consumption parameters are changed more, the result will look better.

	Aq kVt	Rq kVar	Tq kVA	1 kunda
1-davr	89,0	6,0	89,2	kVt soat
2-davr	503,3	34,7	504,5	25 +
3-davr	128,8	6,0	128,9	67,0 0 +
4-davr	302,0	20,8	302,7	25 -
5-davr	267,0	18,0	267,6	25 +

Figure 5. State of consumption values changed up to 25%

Figure 6. The result after changing consumption values up to 25%

Consumers' demand for electricity currently corresponds to the daytime half-peak from 09:00 to 17:00, the morning peak from 06:00 to 09:00, and the

evening peak from 17:00 to 22:00. The times of lowest consumption demand fall significantly between 22:00 at night and 06:00 in the morning.

The results of the calculations show that the use of differentiated electricity tariffs is technically and economically beneficial compared to the use of ordinary tariffs. Reducing peak or peak demand (PIK) and increasing nighttime demand will reduce the overloading of transformers. The indicators of energy consumption in transformers are reduced, and the electrical load graphs are also significantly smoothed.

So, if we change the value of demand for consumption up to 25%, it has been proven that electricity waste can be reduced by 12.1% compared to the current situation.

Conclusion

- it has been proven in detail that it is possible to reduce electricity losses in transformers using differentiated tariffs.
- electricity consumption by consumers of transformers with a capacity of 630 kVA in residential premises is calculated according to current tariffs and compared with differentiated tariffs.
- considered that with the constant use of the differentiated tariff system, the electricity load schedules will be significantly leveled out.
- the dependence of the time-differentiated tariff system on EENHAT for calculating electricity consumption was studied.

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